

Table 1: Participant profile questions.

ID	Question	Scale of response
Q01	Which state are you from?	Acre; Alagoas; Amapá; Amazonas; Bahia; Ceará; Distrito Federal; Espírito Santo; Goiás; Maranhão; Mato Grosso; Mato Grosso do Sul; Minas Gerais; Pará; Paraíba; Paraná; Pernambuco; Piauí; Rio de Janeiro; Rio Grande do Norte; Rio Grande do Sul; Rondônia; Roraima; Santa Catarina; São Paulo; Sergipe; Tocantins.
Q02	What is your level of education?	Undergraduate student; graduate; specialization; master's student; master's degree; doctoral student; doctorate.
Q03	What is your current role in your job?	Software developer; software engineer; requirements analyst; systems analyst; project manager; information security manager; data engineer; data operator; data controller; information security analyst; other.
Q04	How many years of experience do you have in Data Privacy?	Less than 1 year; between 1 and 5 years; between 6 and 10 years; between 11 and 15 years; more than 15 years.
Q05	What is the nature of the organization you work for?	Private company; Federal Public Administration agency; Research/collaboration project; State-owned company (BB, CEF, SERPRO, DATAPREV); Open-source software project; Self-employed; other.
Q06	Have you ever researched or worked with data protection laws?	Yes; no.
Q07	Do you currently research or work with data protection laws?	Yes; no.
Q08	What is your level of experience or knowledge of data protection laws?	None; basic; intermediate; advanced.

Table 2: Questions relating to the validation process.

ID	Question	Scale of response
Q09	Using the privacy compliance guide would help me comply with data protection laws more quickly.	Likert scale (strongly agree; agree; neither disagree nor agree; disagree; strongly disagree).
Q10	Using the privacy compliance guide would make it easier to navigate privacy regulations.	Likert scale (strongly agree; agree; neither disagree nor agree; disagree; strongly disagree).
Q11	Using the privacy compliance guide would help me ensure better protection of users' privacy.	Likert scale (strongly agree; agree; neither disagree nor agree; disagree; strongly disagree).
Q12	Using the privacy compliance guide would help improve the overall efficiency of privacy compliance in my organization.	Likert scale (strongly agree; agree; neither disagree nor agree; disagree; strongly disagree).
Q13	I would use the privacy compliance guide to improve privacy practices in my work.	Likert scale (strongly agree; agree; neither disagree nor agree; disagree; strongly disagree).
Q14	I find the privacy compliance guide easy to use.	Likert scale (strongly agree; agree; neither disagree nor agree; disagree; strongly disagree).
Q15	I find the privacy compliance guide clear and understandable.	Likert scale (strongly agree; agree; neither disagree nor agree; disagree; strongly disagree).
Q16	I find the privacy compliance guide adaptable to different privacy frameworks and laws (e.g. LGPD, GDPR).	Likert scale (strongly agree; agree; neither disagree nor agree; disagree; strongly disagree).
Q17	I believe that the privacy compliance guide requires a lot of prior knowledge about privacy laws to be fully understood.	Likert scale (strongly agree; agree; neither disagree nor agree; disagree; strongly disagree).
Q18	In your opinion, what are the strengths of the privacy compliance guide?	Open.
Q19	In your opinion, what are the weaknesses of the privacy compliance guide?	Open.
Q20	Is there anything you would change in the privacy compliance guide? If so, please explain what you would change.	Open.